

CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING OF TORCH INFECTIONS IN AYURVEDA

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Article Received on: 18/12/2025

Article Revised on: 08/01/2026

Article Published on: 01/02/2026

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18440578>**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Harshitha M. N.^{1*}, Dr. Papiya Jana² (2026). Conceptual Understanding Of Torch Infections In Ayurveda. International Journal of Modern Pharmaceutical Research, 10(2), 04-08.**ABSTRACT**

Introduction: TORCH infections are a major cause of adverse reproductive and perinatal outcomes, including infertility, recurrent pregnancy loss, intrauterine growth restriction, congenital anomalies, and neonatal morbidity. Although these infections are well defined in modern medicine, classical Ayurvedic texts describe several gynecological and obstetric conditions such as *Yonivyapad*, *Garbhasrava*, *Dushta Artava*, *Krimijanya Vyadhi*, *Jataharani*, and *Aupasargika Vyadhi*, which can be conceptually correlated with infectious etiologies. This study aims to understand TORCH infections through the Ayurvedic principles. **Materials and Methods:** Literatures were reviewed from classical textbooks, contemporary books, e-books, and published articles. *Ayurvedic* concepts related to *nidana*, *samprapti*, *lakshana*, and *chikitsa* were critically analyzed and correlated with TORCH infections. **Results and Discussion:** Ayurvedic concepts including *Mithyachara*, *Krimijanya Vyadhi*, *Aupasargika Vyadhi*, *Jataharani*, *Dushta Artava*, and *Jarayu dosha* demonstrate close conceptual similarity to the transmission, placental involvement, and fetal effects of TORCH infections. Classical descriptions of *Yonivyapad*, *Garbhasrava* and *Garbha Vikriti* parallel modern clinical manifestations such as infertility, recurrent abortions, IUGR and congenital anomalies. Ayurvedic management strategies including *Garbhadhana Vidhi*, *dosha-based chikitsa*, *Shodhana* and *Shamanoushadi's* demonstrated favorable reproductive outcomes. **Conclusion:** TORCH infections can be comprehensively understood through *Ayurvedic* principles, offering a holistic approach for prevention and management to improve maternal and fetal outcomes.

KEYWORDS: TORCH infections, *Garbhasrava*, *Dushta Artava*, *Dushita yoni*.**INTRODUCTION**

TORCH infections comprise a group of infections that have special significance in gynaecological and obstetrical practice due to their potential to cause adverse reproductive and pregnancy outcomes. The acronym TORCH includes (T) refers to toxoplasmosis, (O) means "others" and includes syphilis, Hepatitis B, HIV and parvovirus B19, and among others, (R) refers to rubella, (C) relates to cytomegalovirus infection, and (H) to herpes simplex virus infections. The overall TORCH infection positivity rate was 61.1% in India (2017-18)^[1], although further research is needed to clarify the burden of these infections globally. These infections can cause infertility, repeated miscarriages, IUGR and congenital abnormalities in gynaecological and obstetric conditions. In *Ayurveda*, *Yonirogas*, *Garbhasrava*, and *Garbhapata*, *Dushta Artava* is highlighted as a cause, resulting from *Mithyachara* (improper diet and lifestyle) *Krimijanyaja* and *Jataharani*, *Bhutabhisanga*, or *Amanusha Upasarga* have also been explained in ayurvedic literature. These factors can be interpreted as parallels to pathogen transmission, suggesting TORCH infections

OBSERVATION

may be considered a causative factor within this Ayurvedic framework.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Understanding the concept of TORCH infections through *Ayurveda*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Literatures were reviewed from classical textbooks, contemporary books, e-books, and published articles.

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